

Low-Noise Airport Flight and Ground Operations

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Abstract

The transition to low-emission, low-noise aviation requires not only new aircraft technologies but also a systems-level view of their interaction with airport operations and global or regional air traffic and aircraft fleet involved. This study, within the EFACA project, focuses on airport-scale noise impacts of hybrid-electric and hydrogen-fueled aircraft using the model EFACApport. Simulated trajectories from the VALDES design platform, combined with ADS-B data and certified performance metrics, support detailed analysis of taxi, take-off, and landing phases. Noise modeling tools NoiTra and NoBel ensure compliance of the new aircraft designs with ICAO standards. Scenario-based projections assess the cumulative impact of future traffic and fleet evolution.

1. Introduction

Mitigating climate change and reducing greenhouse gas emissions from civil aviation represent one of the most critical and complex challenges facing the sector today [1]. Most European programmes have committed to achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 [2], which raises a fundamental question: how can aviation reconcile ambitious sustainability targets with growing demand? The Waypoint 2050 report (fig.1) offers a blueprint, allocating roughly 6 % of CO₂ reductions to market-based measures, up to 53 % to Sustainable Aviation Fuels, about 7 % to operational and infrastructure improvements, and approximately 34 % to technological advancements in airframe and propulsion [3]. However, deeper analysis — such as that provided by the Clean Aviation Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) — clarifies that meaningful progress beyond incremental improvements requires entirely new aircraft concepts with radically different energy sources, airframe architectures, and powerplant configurations [4]. Examples include hybrid-electric regional aircraft, ultra-efficient short-medium-range airframes, and even hydrogen-powered airliners.

Figure 1: Schematic of the Air Transport Action Group Waypoint 2050 Scenario 3 for CO₂ emissions: aspirational and aggressive technology perspective [3].

At the same time, mitigating noise remains central to public acceptance and regulatory compliance. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) is expected to adopt substantially stricter noise standards by 2035 (Chapters 15 and 16 of Annex 16), which conventional evolutionary improvements alone cannot satisfy. Novel aircraft technologies with electric, hybrid, and hydrogen power plants offer unique opportunities to address climate and noise goals: flexible power management allows noise minimization at the source during take-off, landing, and taxi operations, while enabling new aircraft topologies optimized for lower fuel burn and emissions.

2. EFACA technologies for sustainable aviation

The EFACA project investigates how innovative propulsion architectures can reduce environmental impact while satisfying future regulatory and operational requirements, aligning with the long-term goals of the Clean Aviation SRIA [4]. It focuses [5] on two low-emission aircraft concepts: a hybrid-electric regional turboprop for short-haul operations (Technology A), which combines gas-turbine engines with hydrogen fuel-cell-driven electric motors to cut both fuel burn and community noise; and a modified narrow-body, medium-haul aircraft powered by liquid hydrogen (Technology B). All technical data, performance parameters, and other critical inputs for the acoustic assessment were supplied by the work-package leaders—primarily ANTONOV Company and IVCHENKO-Progress—who provided detailed specifications on aircraft configuration, propulsion integration, and energy systems. A visual representation of these hybrid-electric and hydrogen-powered concepts is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: EFACA aircraft concepts: a) Hybrid turbo-electric propulsion based on a gas turbine engine and fuel cells for regional aircraft; b) Hybrid turbo-electric propulsion based on a gas turbine engine and fuel cells for regional aircraft [6,7]

Technology A. The EFACA project envisions the development of an 80-seat regional hybrid turboprop aircraft featuring a hybrid turbo-electric propulsion system (HTEP or HEP) that integrates a 2,750 hp gas turbine with a 550 hp electric motor powered by hydrogen fuel cells. The aircraft features a novel integrated gearbox that enables flexible propulsion strategies across all flight phases, as well as a new seven-blade propeller. The aircraft is optimized for routes up to 1,000 km at a cruise speed of approximately 500 km/h [6]. Compared to the ATR 72-600, the new design offers an 11 % increase in seating capacity and a 15 % improvement in energy efficiency. Environmental goals are equally ambitious: CO₂ emissions ≤ 48 g/pax-km, NO_x emissions ≤ 1.8 kg per take-off/landing cycle (30 % lower than the ATR 72-600), zero-emission ground operations, and compliance with ICAO Chapter 14 noise standards with quite big margin [6]. Power distribution varies by flight phase: during take-off and climb, ~ 75 % of the thrust is provided by the gas turbine and ~ 25 % by the electric motor; in cruise, the ratio shifts to ~ 80 % and 20 %, respectively.

Technology B. The hydrogen-powered aircraft concept is quite similar to the A320NEO airframe, but the aircraft operates the engines on liquid hydrogen (LH₂), replacing kerosene tanks with two cryogenic LH₂ tanks (≈ 18.8 t) integrated into the fuselage and wing roots. The single-class 140-seat layout and aerodynamic surfaces remain unchanged, minimizing structural redesign. A dedicated hydrogen fuel system supplies both modified turbofan engines and a fuel-cell generator, enabling CO₂-free propulsion and onboard power. With MTOW of ~ 77 t and OEW of ~ 43.6 t, the aircraft supports a 20.8 t payload, achieving a range of 3,600 km (max payload) and up to 7,400 km ferry range, cruising at 840 km/h. Projected fuel efficiency (0.955 MJ/pax-km), and runway requirements (1,770 m take-off / 1,920 m landing) are compatible with existing A320 operations [7].

While novel propulsion systems show promise in reducing noise and emissions, their full impact must be assessed holistically—from the noise signature of a single aircraft to fleet-level exposure at various airports. Interactions between aircraft design, airport infrastructure, and fleet strategies significantly influence the overall effectiveness of decarbonisation and noise mitigation.

To address this, EFACA introduces a three-level framework covering aircraft, airport, and fleet levels, implemented through the VALDES (Vehicle–Airport–Fleet Design and Evaluation Space) platform (Figure 3). VALDES supports multidisciplinary design optimisation (MDO) by integrating engine performance modelling, trajectory generation, and environmental impact assessment. The framework aligns with certification standards, particularly those related to aircraft noise [8]. By combining validated modelling tools with real-world operational data, EFACA aims to show that hybrid-electric and hydrogen-fuelled aircraft can meet or exceed European Green Deal targets for noise and emissions, advancing the path toward sustainable aviation by 2050.

While this multi-level framework enables a comprehensive evaluation, this paper concentrates on *the airport level*, assessing how hybrid-electric and hydrogen-powered aircraft affect noise exposure at regional airports. We examine

specific scenarios during LTO and ground-operation phases, comparing the noise footprints of legacy and novel aircraft. Such an analysis is crucial for understanding the real-world implications of these innovations on nearby communities, infrastructure planning, and regulatory frameworks.

Figure 3: VALDES - modular approach to the evaluation of fuel burn, engine emission, and noise metrics [8]

3. Acoustic Advances in EFACA Aircraft and Corresponding Noise-Footprint Changes

At this stage, the Aircraft Design and Flight Performances Space (ADFPS) (a separate module of the VALDES in figure 3) as part of the VALDES brings together geometric, propulsion, and operational parameters to appraise each concept's environmental footprint—covering noise, fuel consumption, and emissions—against ICAO Annex 16, Volume I standards. Within ADFPS, performance engines such as NoBel, NoiTra, and IsoBella are integrated to simulate both in-flight and ground-level acoustic footprints by ingesting aircraft geometry, engine maps, thrust settings, and flight-path segments, and generating detailed per-segment outputs, such as thrust profiles, pitch angles, and slant ranges to certified observer locations, while certified Noise-Power-Distance (NPD) data from the ANP database and selected validation runs using FAA's INM and AEDT ensure full compatibility with ICAO/CAEP procedures. These outputs feed into sound propagation models (e.g., NoiTra, AEDT), which compute SEL, L_{Amax} , L_{den} , and related indicators by tracing source sound power through directivity and atmospheric attenuation. An embedded flight-dynamics solver divides the mission into climb, cruise, descent, etc., applies ISA corrections, and tracks mass changes from fuel burn, enabling true mission-level consistency and compliance with TLARs. At the aircraft level, standardized ICAO LTO profiles are used to compute key noise indicators—SEL, L_{Amax} , and EPNL—at ground observer locations defined in Doc 9911.

3.1 Hybrid aircraft LTO noise footprint (Technology A).

The new aircraft's performance and noise were modelled using the ADFPS system, developed by Kyiv Aviation Institute (KAI, Ukraine) and ILOT (Poland). The ENGINE and FLIGHT modules generate engine parameters and flight trajectories, while noise sources are simulated via NoiTra and NoBel, with multi-stage validation. The ATR 72-600 (PW127XT) served as the reference aircraft, using certified data from EASA (certification and ANP databases). Noise footprints were modelled at ICAO certification points using AEDT v3e and IsoBella. This enabled benchmarking of the hybrid aircraft and calibration of predictive models. Cross-validation with measurements from Gdansk, Katowice, and Lublin airports showed high consistency with certified values. Recent updates include adjusted NPD curves for the HEP design (Figure 4) and comparative trajectory analyses using ANP data and ADS-B/Flightradar24 (Figure 5). Key metrics, SEL and EPNL, were computed at ICAO observer points to assess the EFACA aircraft's noise profile for single-mission simulations. According to the latest analyses (figure 4), the average NPD correction should be 4 dB for departure and 2 dB for approach, whereas previous-generation ATR 72 NPDs were adjusted by +5 EPNdB (departure) and +2 EPNdB (approach) to match the higher observed noise levels [8].

Hybrid operation enables reduced thrust settings and smoother power transitions during approach and climb. Figure 5 presents corrected altitude and speed profiles for all real-world departures compared against five scenario-based trajectories: STANDARD1, STANDARD2, STANDARD3 (ANP database), UCON (ADS developed model for conventional AT76), and UHYBRID (profile for ADFPS developed model for HEP). The analysis is limited to the

initial climb phase, where noise exposure is most critical due to aircraft proximity to the ground and communities near the airport. In the altitude profile, all scenario trajectories exhibit similar initial climb gradients but differ in their ascent rates. The UHYBRID profile shows a more gradual climb, maintaining a lower altitude over the first 40 nautical miles compared to conventional profiles (e.g., UCON and STANDARD variants). This reflects a noise-optimized trajectory design aimed at reducing the acoustic footprint during the departure phase. The speed profile similarly reveals distinct strategies. While all trajectories initiate with comparable speeds (~130–150 knots), the hybrid scenario (UHYBRID) accelerates more conservatively. In contrast, the STANDARD and UCON profiles reach higher speeds more rapidly, reflecting conventional thrust management. These differences in altitude and speed evolution directly influence engine settings and thrust output, key parameters in predicting noise levels using models such as NoiTra and AEDT.

Figure 4: NPD corrections for EFACA HEP aircraft in comparison with reference aircraft AT 76: a) departure NPDs; b) approach NPDs before (solid) and after (dotted) corrections

Figure 5: Comparison of ANP standard profiles (STANDARD1–3), ADS-developed models for conventional AT76 (UCON) and hybrid-electric propulsion (UHYBRID), with real flight tracking data: a) altitude b) ground speed

Noise at certification points. Table 1 compares lateral, flyover, and approach EPNL values for various ATR 72 configurations based on both certified data and standardized calculations (ISA+10°C). The legacy AT72 shows the highest noise (95.7 lateral, 88.4 flyover, 93.6 approach EPNdB), while certified EASA data for the ATR72-212A (PW127F) reports significantly lower values (82.5–82.6 lateral, 76.3–81.2 flyover, 92.1–92.5 approach). These are close to calculated ANP-based values for the modern AT76 (90.7, 83.4, 91.6). EFACA modelled profiles for AT76 show further reductions, with UHYBRID notably outperforming UCON, especially at lateral and flyover points (72.1–78.9 vs. 81.3–92.7 EPNdB). These results highlight the noise reduction potential of HEP aircraft with optimized trajectories. Figure 6 vividly illustrates these differences.

Table 1: Certificated and calculated EPNL for ATR 72 versions at certification points

Source & AC type	Lateral	Flyover	Approach
Noise DB Cert for ATR-72-500, PW 127F (23000 kg)	82.5	80.5	92.2
EASA Cert Database: ATR72-212A, PW127F	82.5-82.6	76.3-81.2	92.1-92.5
AT72 (NPDs correction + 5. & +2.)	95.7	88.4	93.6
AT76 (ANP v.2.3)	90.7	83.4	91.6
AT76 for the EFACA HEP flight profiles	82.4	75.9	92.2
AT76 for UCON flight profiles	81.3	79.1	92.7
EFACA HEP (NPDs correction - 4. & -2.)	78.9	72.1	91.3

Figure 6: ICAO certification points for *EPNL* assessment in comparison with noise contour 90 EPNdB during the departure (a) and approach (b) for various versions of the ATR-72: AT72 (black line); AT76 – green area; EFACA HEP (white line)

Noise footprints. In the departure view (Figure 6a), the AT72 and AT76 noise contours spill well beyond airport boundaries, whereas the EFACA HEP contour hugs the airfield edge and closes almost immediately after liftoff. The EFACA HEP design dramatically shrinks the departure noise footprint—roughly half the size of the AT76’s—and entirely avoids the ICAO certification points, demonstrating a clear reduction in take-off noise. Its 90 EPNdB contour stays within airport limits and fades out almost immediately after liftoff. However, during the approach, the contour still stretches beyond the airfield, producing a longer, more drawn-out pattern typical of turboprop landings. Even so, the hybrid-electric approach contour, while still encompassing the certification point, is only marginally smaller than the AT76’s, indicating that hybridization delivers modest but tangible noise improvements on final approach. In the approach plot (Figure 6b), all variants still enclose the ICAO certification points, but the hybrid-electric design inscribes a marginally smaller footprint than the conventional AT76, showing that thrust smoothing can yield tangible benefits even in the final approach phase. SEL contour areas for 80–100 dB bands (Figure 7) further highlight the trade-offs. Both UCON and HEP profiles shrink departure contours markedly, yet during approach, the UCON profile’s area drops to just 49–54 % of the ANP standard. Curiously, the HEP approach footprint expands by about 130 % at the 65 dB SEL level—a consequence of its gentler descent profile and unique thrust settings.

Figure 7: Comparison between the reference SELA contours for the departures (a,b) and the arrivals (c,d) of AT76 (filled contours), its UCON version (black lines), and HEP aircraft (white lines)

3.2 Hydrogen aircraft LTO noise footprint (Technology B).

As a benchmark, the noise model for the conventional A320NEO (A320-271N) was established for scaling and validation, with profiles and NPD curves available in the ANP database (version 6.2) and in AEDT (v3.d and later). The preliminary results of the ADS NOISE module have shown that, for the hydrogen-powered aircraft, average NPD

offsets of -2 EPNdB for approach, -4 EPNdB for sideline, and -3 EPNdB for flyover should be applied—totaling a 9 EPNdB reduction across the LTO cycle—which reflects the noise-reduction potential of LH₂ propulsion.

The ADS Flight Profile module enabled the simulation of takeoff and approach trajectories for the conventional (reference) A320NEO and the comparison of these results with the ANP takeoff curves—plotted as distance-vs-altitude and distance-vs-thrust for the approach phase in Figure 8. Compared to both the ANP standard trajectories and the UCON profiles, UHYDRO’s climb and descent use lower thrust settings and gentler power transitions, yielding noticeably tighter and quieter noise contours around the runway and thus significantly shrinking the aircraft’s acoustic footprint. Table 2 summarizes both certified and analytically derived EPNL for the A320-271N under various approach/departure profiles and modelling scenarios, alongside the hydrogen-powered variant. For the Hydrogen variant with appropriate NPD corrections the applying the optimized NPD offsets reduces the conventional aircraft noise model to 89.75 dB lateral, 77.94 dB flyover and 85.05 dB approach, while the HYDRO variant without correction falls to 90.05 dB, 81.36 dB and 85.31 dB, respectively—demonstrating a net 2–3 dB improvement over the predictions.

Figure 8: Comparison of ANP standard approach profiles (App1, App2), ADS-developed models for conventional A320NEO (UCON) and hydrogen propulsion (UHYDRO): a) Altitude b) Thrust per Engine

Figure 9 shows that the hydrogen-powered aircraft (A320-271N_NDPs, HYDRO) produces markedly smaller noise footprints for both departures and arrivals compared to the certified reference and conventional ADS model (UCON). In the departure panels (a, b - Figure 9), the filled contours represent the certified A320NEO LTO footprint at each EPNL threshold, while white lines depict the UCON model and black lines the UHYDRO variant; at every level, such as the 85 EPNdB contour, the UHYDRO outline is visibly more compact, a result of reduced thrust demands and smoother power transitions. On arrival (panels c, d - figure 9), the same trend emerges: the UHYDRO contours lie well within the ST1 baseline and the UCON profile, indicating that hydrogen propulsion focuses acoustic energy more narrowly at touchdown and thus reduces overall noise exposure. Quantitatively, the 70 EPNdB contour areas are 100 % for the reference, 85.7 % for UCON, and 60.0 % for UHYDRO; at 80 EPNdB, they are 100 %, 80.8 %, and 55.6 %, and at 90 EPNdB, 100 %, 61.5 %, and 38.5 %, respectively.

Table 2: Certified and calculated EPNL for A320NEO and Hydrogen at certification points

Aircraft name	Profile	Lateral	Flyover	Approach	MTOW, lbs
A320-271N	APP1/ST5	92.74	85.62	89.36	155820
A320-271N	APP2/ST4	92.74	83.18	89.45	166792
A320-271N	CONV	91.72	80.93	88.25	152118
A320-271N	HYDRO	92.02	84.35	88.81	161598
A320-271N_NDPs	UCON	89.75	77.94	85.05	152118
A320-271N_NDPs	HYDRO	90.05	81.36	85.31	161598
A320-271N	DEP_ICAOA5	-	84.3	89.16	166792
EASA Data for A320-271N	92- 92.6	77.8-82	85.3 - 88	-	-
EASA Data for A320-271N / PW1127G-JM	92-92.4	79.7-80	86.4-86.9	-	-

Hybrid-electric propulsion (*Technology A*) delivers its greatest noise reductions during take-off, with more modest gains on approach, and the hydrogen-powered A320NEO (*Technology B*) amplifies this effect, achieving an overall LTO cycle reduction of about 9 EPNdB. However, meeting the more stringent future ICAO targets will require not only further airframe-source optimizations—such as advanced acoustic liners, refined flight-path procedures, and engine nacelle treatments—but also ICAO’s “balanced” measures like land-use planning, noise-abatement procedures,

and preferential routing. A comprehensive evaluation of these benefits must extend beyond single-aircraft analyses to airport-level assessments that incorporate real operations, fleet mix, and capacity, and ultimately to fleet-level projections under evolving traffic scenarios.

Figure 9: Comparison between the reference EPNL contours for the departures (a,b) and the arrivals (c,d) of A320NEO (filled contours), its UCON model (white lines), and UHYDRO aircraft (black lines)

3.3 Single Ground Operations Noise Footprint

According to previous research [9–11], taxiing and idling in runway queues—especially during peak-hour operations or at night—can contribute to noise contours and cumulative noise indices (e.g., L_{den} , DNL), particularly when taxiways lie close to airport property lines and nearby noise-sensitive areas. Thus, evaluating noise from this ground-operation phase for a new aircraft can be especially critical at regional airports, where turboprops may account for a substantial share of movements. To model noise levels using ADS-B/FR24 flight-tracking data, an inverse thrust-estimation method was implemented: the ground-speed profile $v(l)$ was interpolated with a piecewise cubic Hermite spline (“pchip”) and then resampled using the “interpac” routine to recover the position of aircraft along the flight path, thereby enabling the calculation of total thrust for both engines [12,13]. This lets us express thrust as a continuous function of both time and arc length. Total thrust for two rotors ($n_{rot} = 2$) was modeled to vary linearly between static

(T_{st}) and dynamic (T_{dyn}) values: $T = n_{Rot} \left[T_{st} + \frac{v}{v_{dyn}} (T_{dyn} - T_{st}) \right]$, where $n_{Rot}=2$ is the number of rotors, $v_{dyn}=150$ km/h is the speed at which usage of computations for dynamics thrust becomes valid, static thrust is determined based

on the formula $T_{st} = \sqrt[3]{P^2 \eta_{st}^2 \pi \frac{d^2}{2} \rho}$, where $\eta_{st}=0.65$ is the efficiency of a propeller in static conditions, d is the propeller diameter, ρ is air density in the airport. The dynamic thrust in this case is computed as follows: $T_{dyn} =$

$\eta(v_{dyn}) \frac{P(v_{dyn}, H, \alpha_{PLA})}{v_{dyn}} + T_{jet}(v_{dyn}, H, \alpha_{PLA})$, where α_{PLA} is the power level angle (PLA), H is the geopotential height.

The efficiency of the propeller η was calculated according to the theory of the actuator disk, with a correction according to the formula [14]: $\eta(v) = \frac{2 \cdot 0.885}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{8P}{\rho v^3 \pi d^2}}}$. The dependencies $P(v, H, \alpha_{PLA})$ and $T_{jet}(v, H, \alpha_{PLA})$ originate from the

module for the computation of working processes in the gas turbine engine for PW127F. Estimation of noise was done for aircraft taxiing using two engines. The distance between the engines was taken into account. The direction of movement was extracted from the trajectory to properly orient noise directivity pattern of propellers.

An aircraft mass of 20 t was assumed at the beginning of taxiing, and the ground-speed profile $v(l)$ along with its derivative dv/dl were input into the ground-dynamics equations—accounting for drag (D), lift (L), friction (μ) and taxiway slope—to verify that resulting accelerations remained realistic. We used the data about ground speed and coordinates to construct a cubic spline describing speed dependence on arc length $v(l)$. This cubic spline can be obtained using the Matlab function “pchip”. Acceleration $\frac{dv}{dt}$ can be found from the same spline by differentiation using

the Matlab function “fnder”. Propeller hub positions, calculated from the aircraft’s center of gravity and geometry, were applied in the Gutin–Deming model to estimate instantaneous sound pressure $p(x,y,t)$, with taxi RPM limited to 850 rpm [13] to represent reduced noise levels. SEL was computed for each run without employing a top-cut. In total, 36 ATR 72-600 taxi operations at Gdansk Airport (2024) were analysed to characterize propeller noise during ground movements – some results are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Noise contours for AT76: a) SEL for taxi in operation - sharp turn to the left; b) SEL for taxi out operation - shortest path shown; taxi in operation - sharp turn to the left; c) SELA for taxi in operation - sharp turn to the left; d) SELA for taxi out operation - shortest path shown

The contours of SEL cover more area if the taxiing path is long (Figures 10 a,b) compared to a short taxiing path (Figures 10 a, d). Hence, for noise reduction, it is important to keep taxiing operations as short as possible. As can be seen in Figures 10, a-b SEL increases when the airplane slows down during turns. To minimize noise during taxiing operations, airports should design their taxiways with rounded and smooth curvatures. SEL contours for the airplane that is oriented along the taxiway most of the time stretch in a direction perpendicular to the taxiway because the propeller sound directivity is highest in the plane of propeller rotation. Figures 10, c–d illustrate the noise exposure outcomes following A-weighted corrections (SELA) applied to the same aircraft and flight profiles. SELA values are significantly lower than SEL results and may be comparable with modelling outcomes for single events such as take-off and landing (figures 7), or with cumulative noise levels assessed during the corresponding LTO phases.

These taxi-noise simulations reveal three decisive insights. First, duration and complexity of the taxi path—especially lingering in tight turns—drive SEL far more than modest propulsion changes, so keeping routes as short and straight as possible is paramount. Second, replacing only the turbomachinery with hybrid assistance yields negligible taxi-noise benefits when the gas turbine remains the sole mover; true reductions require operating on electric power alone during ground manoeuvres. Finally, because electric taxiing decouples noise from engine thrust, investing in on-aircraft electric drive or tow-barless tugs will unlock the greatest reductions in community exposure, making electric propulsion the clear priority for next-generation low-noise ground operations.

4. Regional Airport Noise Footprints for Hybrid-Electric and Hydrogen Aircraft

4.1 Noise scenarios at the EFACApport

EFACApport. Detailed modelling at the airport level is essential to demonstrate the benefits of hybrid-electric propulsion (HEP) aircraft in reducing environmental noise in airport vicinities. ATR 72 aircraft are widely used in regional airports, particularly where they do not directly compete with high-speed rail. Evaluating their HEP successors within realistic operational scenarios allows a practical assessment of Technology A (HEP) and its synergies with Technology B (successive generations of narrow-body jets such as A320NEO).

Gdańsk Lech Wałęsa Airport (GDN) was selected for this purpose due to its strategic role in Polish regional aviation and access to detailed noise monitoring data. As a typical European regional airport, GDN offers a diverse fleet mix and consistent traffic patterns. With over 200 daily operations, more than 80% of flights are operated by narrow-body jets (A320, B737), serving short-to-medium range routes across Europe. The airport layout and runway use patterns—RW11 (25%) and RW29 (75%)—are modelled according to observed annual operations, influenced by dominant westerly winds. This setup accurately represents real-world noise exposure from both existing aircraft and EFACA concepts, with the FSDS platform integrating airport layout, traffic data, fleet composition, and temporal variations. Baseline scenarios (AT76 and A320 CEO/NEO) serve as references for assessing noise reduction achieved by EFACA technologies. This integrated assessment supports both fleet-level strategy and future noise zoning improvements in regional hubs.

Operational Airport Scenario for Technology A was developed for a baseline assessment of the contribution of regional aircraft (generic fleet for average regional airport data based on EUROSTAT data [10]). The primary aircraft structure was the following: narrowbody (70%, A320 – representative type), turboprop (21%, AT72), regional jet (7%, EMB145), and widebody (2%, A330). Figure 11 provides generalized data for Scenario A, including fleet category structure and the defined percentage of flights during each period. For the EFACA noise modelling scenario, a representative maximum of 212 daily operations was adopted. To accurately assess L_{den} and L_{night} noise exposure, the time-of-day distribution of flights must be considered: daytime (07:00–19:00), evening (19:00–23:00), and night (23:00–07:00). Based on data from open sources (FR24, FlightAware) and the airport's official statistics, the daily distribution of flights in 2023 at GDN is estimated as 63% during the day, 20% in the evening, and 17% at night.

Figure 11. Baseline A scenario for EFACA airport – aircraft operations by class and time of day

Thus, to evaluate the possible efficiency of future HEP aircraft, a look should be taken at the previous efficiency of noise models and compare the noise performance of the previous generation of the representative aircraft. For this purpose, the following set of calculation cases for Scenario A was developed (table 3).

Case 3 (A320NEO & AT76) is the baseline scenario (100%) for assessing the relative reduction of noise contour areas. All other configurations are compared to it across noise levels of 55–75 dB (L_{den}) and 50–70 dB (L_{night}) – Figures 12–13. The noisiest scenario is Case 0, showing an increase in L_{den} contour area up to 181% at the 55 dB level compared to Case 3. Night-time noise (L_{night}) follows a similar trend, although the impact of new technologies is less pronounced. Case 0 remains the noisiest scenario, reaching up to 229% of Case 3 at the 60 dB level. Hybrid configurations (Case 5+ and 6+) still demonstrate a reduction in noise footprint—approximately 91–98% of the baseline, especially at higher levels (65–70 dB). However, at lower L_{night} levels (50–60 dB), even hybrid variants without NPDs correction (e.g., Case 5+) show only marginal improvement and remain close to Case 3. Cases 1 and 2 (A320CEO_1/2 & AT76anp) show moderate improvements, around 150–160% relative to Case 3. Cases 4 and 5 (UCON and UHYBRID with CEO engines) come significantly closer to the baseline but are still higher, in the 120–140% range. Cases 5+ and 6+, which incorporate hybrid technologies and NPDs correction, demonstrate the best results, reaching as low as 91–96%, corresponding to a 4–9% reduction in noise footprint area compared to Case 3.

Thus, hybrid-electric propulsion configurations (EFACA HEP), especially when combined with corrected NPD curves, such as in Case 6+, demonstrate the most effective reduction in noise contours for both day (L_{den}) and night (L_{night}) metrics, particularly in the 55–70 dB range. These configurations leverage optimized flight profiles (UHYBRID) and advanced power management to minimize acoustic impact during take-off and landing. The benefits are most pronounced at lateral and flyover certification points, where reduced thrust and improved directivity characteristics contribute to measurable noise reductions.

Table 3. Calculation cases for Scenario Analysis, Airport Level

Case	Regional Aircraft	Profile / Tech A	Jet Aircraft /Tech B	Level of Innovation
0	ATR72	Standard	A320 CEO_1	● Previous generation (0%)
1	ATR76anp	Standard	A320 CEO_1	● ATR76 update
2	ATR76anp	Standard	A320 CEO_2	● ATR76+ CEO2 update
3	ATR76anp	Standard	A320 NEO	● Technology B only
4	ATR76	UCON	A320 CEO_1	● Technology A only
4+	ATR76	UCON	A320 NEO	● A + B combined
5	ATR76	UHYBRID	A320 CEO_1	● Hybrid-only
5+	ATR76	UHYBRID	A320 NEO	● A + B combined
6	ATR76_NPD	UHYBRID	A320 CEO_1	● Advanced Hybrid
6+	ATR76_NPD	UHYBRID	A320 NEO	● Full synergy

Figure 12: Heatmap of Noise L_{den} and L_{night} Contour Area as % of Case 3 (A320 & AT76_ANP)

At the same time, generational upgrades of conventional A320 – from older CEO_1 and CEO_2 engine configurations to the A320NEO (analyzed in the EFACA project as Technology B) – also lead to significant noise mitigation, particularly during daytime operations. This is evident when comparing Case 1 and 2 with Case 3, where footprint areas shrink by up to 30% due to more efficient propulsion and aerodynamic refinements. While A320NEO aircraft offer substantial improvements over previous generations, HEP aircraft with NPD correction provide an additional layer of noise reduction. The greatest environmental benefit is achieved through a combined approach, where both Technology A (hybrid propulsion) and Technology B (new-generation jets) are implemented in tandem. This synergy is critical for meeting long-term noise reduction goals and minimizing the acoustic footprint around regional airports. To assess noise exposure effectively, it's essential to evaluate the impact of operations on both runway directions in terms of noise indices. The subsequent cycle of noise maps, accompanied by detailed Tables, presents the noise modelling results for each magnetic course, capturing the effects of both operational directions. This approach provides a comprehensive noise assessment and supports further effective zoning for aircraft operations in the area.

Figure 13: Noise contours for Case 0 (filled coloured areas), Case 3 (black curves), Case 6+ HYBRID (white curves):
a - L_{den} , b - L_{night}

Under realistic conditions, the operation of runways is not equal due to a variety of factors—geographical, geological, meteorological, and others—that create a unique environment for the vicinity of every airport. For EFACApport, which has two runway thresholds, RW11 and RW29, the following flight distribution of operations is applied: 25% for RW11 and 75% for RW29, based on the operational situation observed at the representative Gdansk airport over a year. Figure 14 compares the most polar technologies – AT72+A320 vs. HEP aircraft. Noise contour analysis reveals that the HEP configuration (Case 6+) consistently results in smaller impacted areas compared to the baseline configuration (Case 0, AT72) across all L_{den} and L_{night} levels (Figure 14). For daytime noise (L_{den}), the area reduction reaches up to 15% at 70 dB and remains around 10–13% across other levels. Night-time noise (L_{night}) shows a similar trend, with reductions most pronounced at 55–60 dB, averaging 11–12%. The difference narrows slightly at lower (50 dB) and higher (70 dB) night levels, with less than 9% reduction.

Figure 14: Noise contours for Case 0 (filled coloured areas) and Case 6+ HYBRID (white curves): a - L_{den} , b - L_{night}

Noise assessments were conducted for both runway directions (RW11 & RW29) to confirm consistent improvements across all cases for Scenario A. HEP configurations continue to outperform the reference model, regardless of the operational course, supporting their feasibility for widespread adoption. The introduction of advanced EFACA HEP aircraft with NPDs correction (minus 4 EPNdB for departure and 2 EPNdB for approach) and conventional aircraft configurations, particularly Case 6+, demonstrates a clear reduction in noise contour areas compared to the baseline (Case 0). The most significant reductions are observed at lower noise levels (e.g., 55–60 dB).

Replacing older aircraft models with newer configurations, such as ATR72 and UCON configurations or the HEP models, yields noticeable improvements. In addition to this improvement, significant noise reduction is forecasted for Cases 2 and 3 (A320CEO2 and A320NEO), showing up to 75% smaller L_{den} contours compared to the baseline, illustrating the significant reduction potential of next-gen mid-range jets.

While all advanced cases demonstrate improvements, the degree of noise reduction varies. The hybrid configurations (Cases 5.1 and 6.1) offer the largest reductions, particularly in approach and departure zones, where Case 6.1 achieves reductions up to 16.8% in L_{night} (50–60 dB) compared to the baseline. At higher noise thresholds (65–70 dB), the reductions become less pronounced, with improvements not exceeding 7%.

4.2 Sound exposure for the taxing scenario at the regional airport

Section 4.2 evaluates the SEL generated during taxi operations at a regional airport, presenting both average and maximum SEL contours for a series of representative trajectories. The scenario encompasses 36 representative taxi routes, both inbound and outbound, recorded in 2024 at Gdańsk Airport. All calculations were performed using the

EFACApport platform. Comparisons are made between the baseline ATR 72 and its hybrid-electric variant the – equipped with a seven-blade propeller and electric-assist propulsion, to quantify the noise impact of conventional versus hybrid taxi scenarios. Average SEL per flight for n trajectories was estimated according to the expression:

$$SEL_{av}(x, y) = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\sum_i^n \int_0^{t_i} p^2(x, y) dt}{n \cdot p_0^2}$$

Because the average SEL cannot sufficiently describe SEL for scenario maximum SEL is shown too. Maximum SEL is defined as $SEL_{max}(x, y) = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\max_t \int_0^{t_i} p^2(x, y) dt}{p_0^2}$

The results of the computation of the average SEL are shown in Figures 15 and 16. It is seen that due to the ordinary aircraft motions, every turn of the taxiway causes the enlargement of SEL contours. The noise due to the taxiing of the hybrid variant of the ATR 72, which uses both electric and gas turbine engines, was considered too (Figure 15, b). It was assumed that the hybrid electric aircraft followed the same paths as the ATR 72 base model. This parallel hybrid system allowed the gas turbine engine to have less power to move the airplane forward in flight because of the additional power provided by the electric motor. However, gas turbine engines were operated while the electric engine was switched off during taxiing. Since the engine had less power in this instance, lowering the friction coefficient values was the only change required to follow the same set of trajectories. The system of equations describing aircraft dynamics on the ground was used to verify the friction coefficient values once more. These values appear to be well within the practical range. The propeller rotation frequency was maintained at the same rate as that of the ATR 72 basic model. The hybrid propulsion type was altered to employ a 7-bladed propeller that IP proposed, in contrast to the initial 6-bladed propeller. Gutin and Deming's propeller noise formulation considered the impact of the average chord length and the modified maximum blade thickness. This computation allowed us to build the average SEL (Figure 15a,b) and maximum SEL contours (Figure 15c,d) for the same taxiing scenario in case the hybrid ATR 72 is used.

Figure 15: Sound exposure levels during taxiing operations based on 36 trajectories: (a) average SEL – basic aircraft (ATR 72); (b) average SEL – hybrid configuration; (c) maximum SEL – basic aircraft (ATR 72); (d) maximum SEL – hybrid configuration.

The contours of maximum SEL are shown in Figures 15c,d, also indicating that turns make a significant contribution to producing SEL.

These taxi-noise simulations reveal three decisive insights. First, duration and complexity of the taxi path—especially lingering in tight turns—drive SEL far more than modest propulsion changes, so keeping routes as short and straight as possible is paramount. Second, replacing only the turbomachinery with hybrid assistance yields negligible taxi-noise benefits when the gas turbine remains the sole mover; true reductions require operating on electric power alone during ground manoeuvres. Finally, because electric taxiing decouples noise from engine thrust, investing in on-aircraft electric drive or tow-barless tugs will unlock the greatest reductions in community exposure, making electric propulsion the clear priority for next-generation low-noise ground operations.

5. Aircraft fleet level

The ICAO strategic goal is to eliminate the number of people exposed to AN worldwide and should be analysed at the fleet level. For these purposes, the specific VADLES module is under development now. A critical input for fleet-level noise projections is the underlying air traffic growth, fleet composition, and operational practices over time. To capture these factors, we incorporate a sensitivity analysis based on EUROCONTROL's 7-Year Forecasting in the Post-COVID Era (Figure 16) and recent statistical trends (Figure 17). Figure 16 compares successive forecast vintages (Spring 2020, Spring/Autumn 2023, Autumn 2024, and Spring 2025) against observed IFR movements from 2019 to 2024. The gradual upward revisions—the most notably a 11.9 % increase in the Spring 2025 base forecast for 2029 compared to the Spring 2020 baseline—illustrate how nominal traffic growth assumptions have changed in response to faster-than-expected recovery. Because noise exposure at the community level scales with total movements, such forecasts' shifts directly affect cumulative noise budgets and the required pace of fleet renewal to meet 2050 noise targets. Figure 17 highlights parallel changes in aircraft operational characteristics between 2018 and 2023: average flight distance increased by 8.6 % (from 1,050 km to 1,140 km), average MTOW rose by 3.0 % (to 89.0 tonnes), while cruise levels remained around FL 345–350. Longer routings and heavier aircraft imply higher fuel burn and broader noise footprints per movement, further amplifying the importance of introducing low-noise designs.

Figure 16: EUROCONTROL 7-year forecasts for 2020-2025 and observed IFR flight Source: EUROCONTROL CRCO and STATFOR.

Figure 17: EUROCONTROL data: Evolution of average flight distance, aircraft MTOW, and cruise flight level for IFR flights in Europe, 2018–2023. Source: EUROCONTROL CRCO and STATFOR.

Noise Metrics. To complement the scenario-based fleet trajectories and assess their long-term noise impact at the community level, this study incorporates a set of integrated cumulative noise indicators. While aircraft-level metrics such as, EPNL, SEL and L_{Amax} offer valuable insights into single-event exposure, they are limited in assessing aggregate effects over time and across a full operational day. Therefore, for fleet-level and airport-scale planning, we employ extended metrics such as L_{den} , which accounts for both the number and timing of events using time-of-day penalties; Noise Energy (cumulative linearized SEL across all movements); and NEF (Noise Exposure Forecast), a well-established planning indicator used in North America and adopted in various long-term airport studies. Each of these metrics enables a time-integrated, traffic-weighted evaluation of noise impact, facilitating scenario-based optimization of fleet composition, airport operation strategies, and regional land-use planning.

NEF is particularly suited for long-term fleet-level assessment because it encapsulates the total daily acoustic energy exposure from a full set of aircraft movements, taking into account both aircraft type and operation frequency. It is

computed as: $NEF = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \sum_{i=1}^N 10^{\frac{EPNL_i - EPNL_{base}}{10}}$, where N is the number of daily operations, $EPNL_i$ is the EPNL for the i -th aircraft type, and $EPNL_{base}$ is a normalization reference value (in this study, based on a modern conventional aircraft representative of current-generation regional or narrow-body jets, such as the A320NEO or AT76). This formulation assumes logarithmic summation of perceived noise energy from all movements, allowing the construction of annual NEF contours and trends under different technology adoption scenarios.

The model is applied for the forecast period 2025–2050, using three illustrative scenarios: Baseline Scenario, where the fleet evolves under EUROCONTROL’s base traffic growth projection without technological shift; HEP Scenario, with progressive replacement of conventional turboprops with hybrid-electric aircraft (HEP-80) starting from 2035; and Hydrogen Scenario, where hydrogen-powered medium-range aircraft (LH2) are introduced on longer routes from 2035/2040 onward.

Each scenario uses a consistent methodology of combining projected movement volumes, fleet composition, and aircraft specific EPNL or SEL values (derived from certification databases or acoustic modelling), matched to actual or projected EFACA reference types. By applying NEF (alongside L_{den} and cumulative noise energy), we can translate fleet-level innovations into spatial and population-based noise metrics, assess whether ICAO and ACARE targets for community noise exposure reduction can be met under each scenario, and support multi-level alignment between aircraft design, operational planning, and airport infrastructure development. The integration of these indicators allows stakeholders to transition from descriptive noise modelling to strategic optimization, where environmental performance becomes a quantitative design driver at both the aircraft and fleet scale.

Conclusions

The VALDES platform was jointly developed within the EFACA project to evaluate the environmental performance of two key technological concepts in Clean Aviation SRIA: hybrid-electric regional turboprops and hydrogen-fuelled narrowbody jets. It enables detailed, multi-level analysis across aircraft, airport, and fleet dimensions, integrating aerodynamic, propulsion, and noise modelling capabilities. This study demonstrates the potential of hybrid-electric aircraft to reduce airport noise, particularly during take-off and approach operations. Using validated EFACA trajectories and certified acoustic data, we observed meaningful reductions in EPNL and SEL values compared to legacy aircraft, with the greatest benefits achieved through optimized thrust settings and adapted NPD corrections. At the aircraft level, the modelled HEP configuration achieved up to -11 dB EPNL at lateral and flyover points and -1.4 dB on approach compared to baseline AT72 values. When NPD corrections were included (-4 dB for take-off, -2 dB for landing), the departure footprint above 90 EPNdB was reduced by almost 50%.

During ground operations, hybrid aircraft also demonstrated lower noise levels during taxiing, typically by 3–5 dB SEL, due to reduced propeller RPM (limited to 850 rpm) and more favourable directivity characteristics. The taxi-noise simulations were included in scenario noise assessment because of their departure 90 EPNdB footprint reduction and revealed three decisive insights. First, keeping taxi routes as short and straight as possible is paramount for noise management due to the duration and complexity of the taxi path—especially lingering in tight turns—drive SEL far more than modest propulsion changes. Second, replacing only the turbo-gas machinery with hybrid assistance yields negligible taxi-noise benefits when the gas turbine remains the sole mover; true reductions require operating on electric power alone during aircraft ground manoeuvres in the airport. Finally, because electric taxiing decouples noise from engine thrust, investing in on-aircraft electric drive or tow-barless tugs will unlock the greatest reductions in community exposure by noise, making electric propulsion the clear priority for next-generation low-noise ground operations.

At the airport level, the study evaluates the noise reduction potential of HEP aircraft at the airport level using the EFACApport model based on real-world operations at Gdańsk airport. A comprehensive set of traffic scenarios was modelled to assess the effectiveness of Technology A (HEP turboprops) and Technology B (successive A320-class jets) in reducing the cumulative noise exposure (Figures 12-14).

Advanced HEP configurations with optimized profiles and NPD corrections compared to the reference scenario with conventional AT76 and A320NEO reduce noise footprints by 4–9% relative to the baseline, especially in the 55–70 dB (L_{den}) and 50–65 dB (L_{night}) ranges. Noise improvements are consistent across both runway directions (RW11, RW29), confirming the robustness of the modelling. Importantly, the combined adoption of both Technology A and B yields the most significant benefit. This synergy supports EFACA’s strategic vision for noise mitigation at regional hubs, showing that hybrid-electric aircraft can meaningfully reduce acoustic impact during take-off and landing while also enhancing compliance with long-term noise zoning goals.

At the fleet level, scenario-based projections indicate that the adoption of hybrid propulsion alone can contribute significantly to ICAO’s long-term noise exposure reduction targets. The scenario analysis also highlights the importance of considering both traffic growth and aircraft replacement dynamics in future policy and infrastructure planning.

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References

- [1] United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). 2015. Paris Agreement. United Nations.
- [2] European Commission. 2020. European Green Deal. Publications Office of the European Union.
- [3] van der Sman, K., M. Bertoli, A. Boon, et al. 2021. Waypoint 2050: Pathways to a Sustainable Air Transport System. ACARE..
- [4] Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking (CAJU). 2021. Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). Clean Aviation.
- [5] EFACA Consortium. 2024. Environmentally Friendly Aviation for All Classes of Aircraft Project Description. EFACA Project Deliverable D1.1.
- [6] Fil, S., Khaustov, A., Berbenets, D., Bondarchuk, O., & Urban, O. (2023). EFACA Deliverable D7.3 Preliminary *shaping of the concept and typical flight profile of the aircraft with HTEP: Preliminary requirements for HTEP* (Grant Agreement No. 101056866)
- [7] ANTONOV Company. (2025, April 9–10). Feasibility study report for the aircraft (D8.4) [WP8: Aircraft with liquid hydrogen fuel for gas turbine power plant]. Presented at the EFACA Consortium Meeting, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy.
- [8] Makarenko, V., Tokarev, V., Kazhan, K., Synylo, K., Yakushenko, O., Zaporozhets, O. (2024) Analysis of fuel consumption and noise of a regional turbo-propeller aircraft with a hybrid power plant. *International Journal of Sustainable Aviation*, 10(4), pp. 315–349. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSA.2024.142562>
- [9] Page, J. A. 2014. Turbofan and Propeller Aircraft Taxi Operating State Noise Power Distance and Spectral Class Database Development Process for AEDT. In: AIAA 2014-0366, Community Noise and Sonic Boom Session. Published Online 10 Jan 2014. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2014-0366>
- [10] Airport Cooperative Research Program. 2013. Enhanced Modeling of Aircraft Taxiway Noise, Volume 2: Aircraft Taxi Noise Database and Development Process. ACRP Web-Only Document 9. Transportation Research Board, Washington, DC. https://onlinepubs.trb.org/onlinepubs/acrp/acrp_webdoc_009.pdf
- [11] National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2009. Enhanced Modeling of Aircraft Taxiway Noise, Volume 1: Scoping. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/22992>.
- [12] D’Errico, J. 2025. *Distance based interpolation along a general curve in space. interparc*. MATLAB Central File Exchange. Available at: <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/34874-interparc>.
- [13] Flight Crew Operating Manual. 1999. ATR 72. Blagnac. Available at: <https://aviation-is.better-than.tv/atr72fcom.pdf> (Accessed: 14 March 2025).
- [14] Lenssen, R.H. 2016. *Series Hybrid Electric Aircraft Comparing the Well-to-Propeller Efficiency With a Conventional Propeller Aircraft*. Delft University of Technology Repository. Available at: <http://repository.tudelft.nl/>.